

MOTIVATION: DOES IT MAKE SENSE?

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Motivation: Does It Make Sense?

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the effects of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. It presented also the advantages, disadvantages and importance of motivation towards top students' excellence among freshmen College of Education students of CapSU – Main Campus having an average of 90 (1.75) and above as top students of the class. With the use of descriptive qualitative phenomenological method, results revealed that most of the top students were extrinsically motivated with their family, friends and God and only few were intrinsically motivated with their goals and future. Intrinsically motivated students are motivated without expecting any reward and they do not let themselves to be left out and be disappointed; while extrinsically motivated students are motivated with the praises, encouragements and rewards to perform well in school. Intrinsic motivation helps students to excel in class, know how to be patient, diligent and independent in their studies, be satisfied on whatever their successes are and forget their unhappy moments that down them in their life as a top student. Extrinsic motivation, on the other hand, builds students' self-confidence and self-esteem, maintains high grades, gives happiness, and motivates them to excel in school with the rewards, praises and encouragements. Intrinsic motivation makes sense because it serves as an inspiration of students to excel in classes and extrinsic motivation as the strength of students to excel in school and help them be confident with a given rewards and praises.

Keywords: *motivation, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation*

Introduction

Everyone wants a specific reason for a specific action. This is same case with academic excellence of a student. They need a reason or motivation to excel in their performances (Haider, et al., 2015). Every student has its own motivation to perform well in classes especially the students in today's generation where school works load them. Their motivations help them build and gather courage to accomplish a certain task and excel academically.

Motivation is a psychological process which leads anyone to act in a way that helps them fulfill unsatisfied needs (Latham, 2011). It plays a significant role in education and it is the fundamental recipe in success. Basically, there are two types of motivation: intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation (Elen, 2017).

Intrinsic motivation occurs if the motivation came from the internal interest of a student that enabled them to perform well in school. On the other hand, extrinsic motivation is when a student perform well in school because of external factors like rewards promised to them (Haider, et al., 2015). Students, especially those who were on the top list, aim to excel in school because they were motivated. They study well, work hard, wait patiently and endure the sleepless nights just to finish a task. Almost all of the students don't want a poor performance. No one ever desired to fail rather they are trying everything at their best to succeed with the help of the support of the family, friends and even teachers who continuously motivate them.

When a student fails, they never give up easily because they have the motive to succeed and receive an award afterwards. Though they wanted to stop and quit still they chose to rest and move forward for their motivation fixes their broken selves and gives them hope to go on. Motivation really helps the student to do well in school.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aims to determine the effects of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation towards top students' excellence. Specifically, it seeks answers to the following questions:

1. What is the top students' motivation in excelling academically in classes?
2. How do intrinsically motivated students excel?
3. How do extrinsically motivated students excel?
4. What are the advantages/disadvantages of intrinsic/extrinsic motivation towards the students?
5. How can motivation make sense in students' life?

Literature Review

Motivation

According to Brown (2010), the word motivation came from the root word as "motion". So, motivation invigorates and energize behavior. Similar with Brown's statement is a Maehr and Meyer's, a description of motivation that was mentioned by Brophy (2010) in his book, "Motivating Students to Learn", wherein motivation was defined as a theoretical construct used to explain the initiation,

direction, intensity, persistence and quality of behavior, especially goal-directed behaviors. Brophy further explained that motives are hypothetical constructs used to explain why people do what they do. Motives are relatively general needs or desires that energize people to initiate purposeful action sequence.

In the classroom context, the concept of student's motivation is used to explain the degree to which students invest attention and effort in various pursuits, which may or may not be the one's desired by their teachers. Student motivation is rooted in student's subjective experiences, especially those connected to their willingness to engage in learning activities and their reasons for doing so (Brophy, 2010). According to Elliot and Dweck that was mentioned by Ayub (2010), motivation is a significantly important factor for academic learning and achievement across childhood through adolescence it is an important contributor to student achievement.

Intrinsic Motivation

Intrinsic motivation encourages behaviors for their own sake (Brown, 2010). It refers to being in an activity for itself, and the pleasure and satisfaction derived from participation (Ayub, 2010). Hartzell (2018), states that intrinsic motivation provides that personal pat on the back that reflects a person's ability, competency, growth, knowledge and self-control over their endeavors. According to Rath (2015), emerging research suggests that it is better to focus solely on intrinsic motivation, because deriving any motive whatsoever from external incentives could decrease performance. To support this claim, he mentioned Wrzesniewski and her team's research about Westpoint Military Cadets where they discovered that Cadets who entered West Point because of internal motivations were more likely to graduate, become commissioned officers, receive promotions, and stay in the military compared with those who entered due to external motives. In a classroom, Warmuth (2014), describes intrinsic motivation as an inherent interest in pursuing a topic (learning for learning's sake) where in a student or an individual find a subject enjoyable and they will naturally desire to learn mastery of it. Intrinsic motivation is doing something for the sake of personal satisfaction (Mulvahill, 2018).

Extrinsic Motivation

Having a job, going to work and caring out the tasks assigned is something people do because they receive something in return for their effort (Buelens, et al., 2010). According to Cherry (2018), extrinsic motivation refers to behavior that is driven by external rewards such as money, fame, grades, and praise. This type of motivation arises from outside the individual, as opposed to intrinsic motivation, which originates inside of the individual. It is similar with Warmuth's (2014), as he refers it to a desire to pursue a subject for reasons outside of the individual, such as rewards, grades, parental or instructor approval, etc. These individuals are motivated to learn a subject not because they want to learn it, but because learning the material will get them good grades, etc. Psychological forms of extrinsic motivation can include praise and public acclaim. A child might clean her room in order to receive positive praise from her parents. An actor might perform in a role in order to obtain attention and acclaim from his audience. In both examples, while the reward is not physical or tangible, it is a type of motivating reward that is external to the actual process of participating in the event (Cherry, 2018).

Extrinsic motivation has a big power and with right use can lead to high results. External rewards can stimulate interest and participation in which person has not had initial interest. Praises are able to induce to obtain new skills or knowledges in the moment when people have studied more they become more motivated intrinsically. External rewards can be a good sign that a worker does a good job and give a chance to understand that their performance is achieved reinforcement (Cherry, 2018). Extrinsic motivation is much easier to establish once the teacher knows what the student is willing to work for. Whether it is stickers, a bit of extra free time or some sort of prize, students usually have a reward they value. An extrinsic reward system can teach students to put in hard work in order to get a reward, another life skill. However, extrinsic motivation often does not work over the long term. Once the rewards or punishments are removed, students tend to lose their motivation. Extrinsic motivators don't get students truly engaged in their learning, they make school analogous to a job—something that has to be done. Furthermore, research indicates that extrinsic rewards can have a negative impact on intrinsic motivation ("Intrinsic vs Extrinsic. The Challenge of Motivation," 2018).

Methodology

Research Design

This study used descriptive qualitative phenomenological method. Descriptive research describes existing conditions without analyzing relationships among variables. The nature of situation as it exists at the time of the conduct of the study was explored fully and carefully examined as its actual phenomenon. Descriptive research typically describes what appears to be happening (Fraenkel and Wallen, 2010). A qualitative approach was also used which is explained as a form of narrative description and observations that occur in more natural and less controlled research setting. This often used special methods to collect data, which emphasizes in-depth descriptions of persons, behaviors and context (Lomax and Fink, 2010).

Moreover, this study is a phenomenological study which attempts to set aside biases and preconceived assumptions about human experience, feelings and responses to a particular situations. This is typically conducted through the use of in-depth interviews of small samples of participants (Georgi, 2012).

Respondents

The respondents of this study were eight (8) College of Education freshmen students of Capiz State University – Main Campus, Roxas

City, Capiz having an average of 90 (1.75) and above because they are the top students of the class.

Instrument

The study used an interview schedule as one of the data collections. In-depth interview was the major method used by the researchers in gathering significant information from the respondents. The interview consisted of seven questions: (1) As a top student, what is your motivation to excel in your classes? (2) How can your motivation help you excel among other students? (3) How are you motivated as a top student of your class? (4) From 1-10, 1 as the least and 10 as the highest, how can you rate the effectiveness of your motivation to your excellence, why? (5) What are the advantages of your motivation to yourself? (6) What are the disadvantages of your motivation to you? (7) What is the importance of motivation in you being a top student?

The interview questions aimed at eliciting relevant information concerning the sense of motivation in the students' performance in class. The instrument was designed in a simple and clear manner that is easy to understand. Cellular phones were also used to gather the answers of the respondents and to record the in-depth interview scenario with the permission of the respondents.

The researchers' interview guide were subjected to validity and reliability testing on its content. The result of the validation suggested the revision of questions to avoid redundancy in the answers.

Procedure

The following procedures were done in the analysis of the data gathered: The data in the study were gathered based on the results of the in-depth interview to the respondents. The researchers asked permission first from the University's authorities and offices. Having established the validity and reliability of the questionnaire, the research questions were administered to the probable respondents.

Upon the approval of the request, the identified participants' consent was sought. The researchers also asked the availability of their time and the permission to take pictures and record the conversation. Upon the respondents' consent, the interview was done afterwards.

The discussion during the in-depth interview was captured through a voice recorder and pictures. Moreover, the researchers was requested the respondents to answer honestly the finalized research questions. When the in-depth interview was accomplished, data were retrieved immediately and analyzed by the researchers. The findings were analyzed based on the processed data and were reviewed several times.

Ethical Considerations

Since the respondents shared some of their insights and opinions regarding with this study, strict measures were taken in presenting their identities. They were given the choice whether to include their names and other personal profiles or not to. However, their consent was sought as to their willingness to be recorded and for their pictures to be taken during the interview.

Results and Discussion

The presentation, analysis and interpretations were in accordance with the information sought for and found in the preconceived questions of the study using the thematic analysis. The themes identified in the data both in intrinsic and extrinsic are: (1) socio-demographic profile; (2) the motivation of top students; (2) effects of motivation to top students; (3) the advantages of motivation; (4) disadvantages of motivation and; (5) importance of motivation to students.

Intrinsically Motivated Students

Motivation

The motivation of intrinsically motivated students comes from the inside and not minding the outside factors. It could be their goals, dreams and future. Based on the result, only two (2) students are intrinsically motivated and their motivations are their goals in life to be achieved and the bountiful and successful future for themselves. According to Rath (2015), it is better to focus solely on intrinsic motivation, because deriving any motive whatsoever from external incentives could decrease performance.

Effects of Intrinsic Motivation

Intrinsically motivated students are more focused in achieving their goal. They became competitive and they do not care to other person specifically when it comes to performances and examinations. Their learnings also remained in their mind for a long period of time. Moreover, they are more resistant and are not easily down in their failures. They take every learnings seriously.

According to the results, intrinsically motivated students feel good and proud when their goals are achieved even without expecting any rewards. Moreover, they do not let themselves to be disappointed, left out and they do not let the problems swallow them.

Respondent 1 answered about intrinsic motivation by stating that "...ginaset ko guid akon mind nga muna dabi kinanglan ko muna... Indi ko dapat i-disappoint akon self kay syempre akon kuntra akon man nga self." (I have that in mind what I should prioritize... I must not disappoint myself which serves as my greatest challenger also to achieve something.)

The result supported Hartzell (2018), states that intrinsic motivation provides that personal pat on the back that reflects a person's ability, competency, growth, knowledge and self-control over their endeavors; while praises are able to induce to obtain new skills or knowledges in the moment when people have studied more, according to Cherry (2018).

Advantages of Intrinsic Motivation

The advantages of being intrinsically motivated students are: their learnings stay on their minds over a long period of time. Students strive hard and never give up. They tend to be more responsible and can do many things and learn fast.

Results showed that if students are intrinsically motivated, they excel more likely in class. They know how to be patient, diligent and independent in their studies. Furthermore, students became satisfied on whatever their successes are and they forget their unhappy moments that down them in their life as a top student.

“So, ang akon tanan nga ginubra from the start nagadula man, especially ang unhappy moments.” (So, what all I did from the start were not sustained especially the unhappy moments) as stated by respondent 3.

Disadvantages

Students with intrinsic motivation are self-centered, competitive as a result they are stressed compared to other students. Based on the result, intrinsically motivated students are pressured due to stress.

It is supported by respondent 5 that, *“Syempre tungod sa motivation ko nga muni nape-pressure akon kaugalingon kag gaabot ang time nga daw masuko nagid ako kay syempre grabe na ang stress, super-duper.”* (I was pressured also by my self-motivation and it came to a point that I want to quit already because of too much stress.)

Importance of Motivation

Intrinsic motivation is important to students because intrinsically motivated students learn more and truly. In this kind of motivation, application to learnings are really seen and the education towards the students are important and became useful in their lives because this is their inspiration.

Results showed that intrinsic motivation serves as the inspiration of students to excel in classes and became progressive also, this is the factor that encourages them to complete a task and learn.

This intensifies as respondent 9 said that, *“Motivation is very important because it pushes you to your limits, this serves as an inspiration kag...muna lang.”* (Motivation is very important because it pushes you to your limits. This serves as an inspiration and...that's all.)

Extrinsically Motivated Students

Motivation

Extrinsic motivations are motivations or reasons upon their performance in school. These are the motivations that come from the outside factors like family, friends, rewards, praises, etc.

Based on the results, extrinsic motivation of students is more likely their family, friends, and God. Out of eight (8) respondents, six (6) are extrinsically motivated as supported by Cherry (2018), stating that extrinsic motivation is much easier to establish once the teacher knows what the student is willing to work for.

Effects of Extrinsic Motivation

Extrinsically motivated students are more likely to depend on others. They tend to give up easily if they feel physically, mentally and emotionally tired. However, they are more motivated to excel in school if they are always appreciated, recognized or praised by people around them. Moreover, they also perform well in school if rewards await them after they can accomplish certain tasks in school.

According to the study, extrinsically motivated students are likely to perform well with praises, rewards, appreciations and support they get from the people around them.

“They are always supporting me in my difficult times. Sila ang gahatag sa akon permi sang strength. Then, kung daku o damo ang problema sila ang gahambal sang dapat ko ubrahon kag gina buligan nila ako para masolve ini.” (There are people who are always supporting me in my life's difficult times. They always give me strength. Then, they help me solve my problems by advising me what to do.) as stated by respondent 2 as being an extrinsically motivated student.

Advantages

Extrinsic motivations are helpful because it serves as an energy that charge them up to take a step forward despite of the negative impacts that may encounter along the way. Extrinsic motivations are helpful in times of their trouble. Based on the study, students who are extrinsically motivated believes that extrinsic motivation develops their self-confidence and self-esteem. It maintains their high

grades, gives them happiness, helps them achieve their goals, excel in school, making others proud, receiving rewards, strive hard and helps them enter school.

“Nabuligan mo nga maging better person. Nabuligan ko nga maging kung ano ko yanda. Tag-as akong grades, naa-achieve ko akong goals. Ginahatagan ako sang courage kag determination to pursue the things I dream”, (I helped myself to become a better person of what I am right now. My grades become higher and I achieved my goals. My motivation gave me courage and determination to pursue the things I dreamt.) said by respondent 2.

The statement by the respondent was agreed by Brown (2010), which said that motivation invigorates and energize behavior of a student.

Disadvantages

Extrinsically motivated students tend to trust and depend to others more than themselves. They tend to give up easily if their activities or outputs make them exhausted or tired. Moreover, extrinsically motivated students are pressured because they fear if they cannot meet the expectations of others.

According to the study, an extrinsically motivated students have no time for enjoyment. Extrinsic motivation leads to fear of failure and paranoia. It leads to pressure, craziness, comparison or worse health problem due to staying up late at night.

“Ang disadvantages naman sang akon motivation kay kung masubrahan na ka motivated ang tawo kay syempre kis-a pressured kag daw mabuang na kay damu-damo na school works. I don’t want my family to be disappointed, I’m afraid nga kung mag-fail ako sa school, ma-disappoint sila sa akon, so that’s why daw wala na ko pahuway magtuon kag mag-ubra sang school works just to do my best at school.” (The disadvantages of self-motivation is when it goes beyond from what is needed and it will cause too much pressure that made me mad of overloaded school works. I don’t want to disappoint my family. I’m afraid that if I will be failed in school, they will be disappointed also. So, for me to do my best, I keep on studying and do my school works.) according to respondent 4.

Importance

Motivation of extrinsically motivated students more likely to be the people that is always behind them in the ups and downs of their lives. It serves as the source of strength and encouragement to continue in striving hard despite of the challenges that comes on their way. Moreover, these motivations boost their confidence and the reason why they like to go to school every day.

According to the study, extrinsically motivated students sees their motivation as their source of strengths. It encourages them to do better in school and it also lifts their spirit to conquer the challenges they face in everyday life. Extrinsically motivated students are confident.

According to respondent 4, *Ang important sa akon education is sila (family) ang gahatag sa akon strength para ubrahon ko akon ulubrahon kag kung wala ko motivation, wala ko di sa eskwelahan. Syempre kung motivated ako permi ako gasulod kag ga excel sa eskwelahan and ga-boost man akon confidence by just thinking nga this is all for them.” (My family is important to my education and my motivation for they give me strength to do my school works. If I am motivated, I always come to school and excel. It boosts my confidence for what I am doing are intended also for them.)* stating how important extrinsic motivation also.

Conclusions

Most of the top students were extrinsically motivated with their family, friends and God and only few were intrinsically motivated with their goals and future.

Intrinsically motivated students are motivated within without expecting any rewards and they do not let themselves to be left out and be disappointed; while extrinsically motivated students are motivated with the praises, encouragements and rewards to perform well in school. Furthermore, intrinsically motivated students excel more compared to the extrinsically motivated students.

Intrinsic motivation helps students to excel in class, know how to be patient, diligent and independent in their studies, be satisfied on whatever their successes are and forget their unhappy moments that down them in their life as a top student. Extrinsic motivation, on the other hand, builds students’ self-confidence and self-esteem, maintains high grades, gives happiness, and motivates them to excel in school with the rewards, praises and encouragements.

On the other hand, intrinsically motivated students are pressured due to stress. Since intrinsic motivation comes from inside will, the student can be very vulnerable to stress and disappointments that can affect its behavior and performance inside the classroom. Extrinsic motivation results to having no time for enjoyment, leads to fear of failure, craziness, pressure, comparison or worse health problem due to staying up late at night.

Intrinsic motivation makes sense because it serves as an inspiration of students to excel in classes and extrinsic motivation as the strength of students to excel in school and help them be confident with a given rewards and praises.

The researchers recommended that every student may consider the motivational factors, either intrinsic or extrinsic, depending on their

own choice, for them to perform well in their classes and achieve their goals.

Moreover, it is suggested for the teachers and parents to continue motivating the students so that they will be able to perform well and excel in their classes. Knowing more the students' attitudes and personalities by the teachers and parents may be given importance for them to motivate appropriately and necessarily.

Furthermore, it is better if the students may have both the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation for themselves so they may improve their source of motivation. Through practicing their minds to motivate themselves and allowing external factors like their family, school recognitions and awards may be effective considerations.

Lastly, the researchers recommend a further research about this study to dig deeper and to fully understand the factors that affect the performance of students.

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